

Guidelines For Surgical Procedures Conducive To Bone Grafting

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The mechanism of periodontal regeneration is still a mysterious and intricate occurrence. In the modern era of dentistry, bone grafting has become an invaluable clinical treatment for a range of reconstructive uses. Various regeneration treatment approaches have been utilized and implemented in clinical settings throughout the past ten years. It is commonly known that the results of periodontal regeneration operations are improved by bone transplants and bone substitutes. Periodontists currently prefer using bone as a grafting material since it has demonstrated clinical efficacy, functional periodontal repair, filling of visible bone defects, and pocket reduction to acceptable levels. Particulate grafts have primarily been applied to treat small bone defects like fenestrations and dehiscence. Particulate grafting has a success rate ranging from 85.7% to 100% and very few problems. When autografts were paired with xenografts, HA, or homologous bone, a higher success rate was noted.

According to Brunel et al. and Pieri et al.,^{1,2} grafts are not used in the following cases:

- ✓ Patients who smoke more than ten cigarettes a day;
- ✓ Patients with severe liver or kidney disease;
- ✓ Patients who have previously received head and neck radiation therapy;
- ✓ Patients who are uncontrolled diabetics;
- ✓ Patients who have active periodontal disease in the residual dentition;
- ✓ Patients who have autoimmune or inflammatory disorders of the oral mucosa;
- ✓ Noncompliant patients; and any other medical condition that contraindicates oral surgery when the anatomic factors are unfavourable.

Indications of Bone Grafts:^{3,4}

1. Bone Defects;
 - Two-walled and three-walled deep intraosseous defects,
 - Retention of teeth that may need more bony support,
 - Augmentation of bone support for abutment teeth,
 - Bone abnormalities linked to juvenile periodontitis
 - Defects in furcation: Grade II, III
 - Ridge enhancement Regrowing bone surrounding the implants
 - Bone deficiency at the donor site.

Many attempts have been made to regenerate periodontal defects, including intrabony and furcation defects. Many clinicians support the use of DFDBA owing to its faster release of growth factors which promotes better periodontal regeneration. DFDBA may also be combined with other additional regenerative materials like enamel Matrix derivatives or PRF. DFDBA may also be combined with FDBA in a ratio of 70/ 30 to provide some additional stability of the graft while maintaining the core protein release potential from the DFDBA.

2. Sinus Augmentation: Sinus is one of the most challenging areas to regenerate. To overcome this many clinicians have advocated using PRF in combination with graft procedure. Clinicians have recommended using a combination of FDBA and a non resorbable xenograft for sinus augmentation procedure, typically done in a ratio of 1:1 .
Clinical Goals of Bone Grafting for Periodontal Regeneration:
Patients with periodontitis should aim for the following results from bone

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grafting procedures:

1. Bone fill of the osseous defect
2. Gain in clinical attachment
3. Probing depth reduction
4. New bone, cementum, and periodontal ligament regeneration

What Are the Perfect Features of a Bone Graft?

- ✓ Nontoxic to the human body
- ✓ Should not provoke an inflammatory response
- ✓ Should be able to withstand infection
- ✓ Should not lead to Ankylosis or root resorption
- ✓ Should be strong and resilient
- ✓ Should be Easily mouldable
- ✓ Easily and sufficiently available
- ✓ Should require a minimal surgical technique.
- ✓ Encourages the formation of new attachment

Requirements for a Successful Graft: When doing bone grafts for periodontal regeneration, the following surgical factors are crucial:

Patient Selection

When it comes to the application and outcome of regenerative medicine, especially bone grafting, careful consideration of the patient is very crucial. The patient needs to show that they are highly motivated and capable of doing daily plaque removal. To maintain their periodontal health, patients must also demonstrate a dedication to keeping the frequently drawn-out and demanding sessions. During these, the patient's progress is assessed using a plaque index assessment and baseline records. The patient's emotional state, habits (especially smoking), and capacity for long dental visits are other issues that need to be taken into account.

Selection of Materials

Matching a defect's outlines to the right treatment is crucial for any augmentation or regenerative procedure. For example, a graft's chance of success increases with the number of bone walls present in the defect site. Choosing a treatment for a defect that won't respond well to the surgery is a major cause of failures. Generally speaking, the greater the defect, the more crucial it is to use autogenous bone since it offers the highest possible levels of cellularity and structure for the formation of new bone. For a variety of reasons, cancellous bone is preferred over cortical bone when using autografts or allografts. Revascularization occurs more quickly with cancellous grafts, which increases the likelihood of preserving more osteogenic cell

Bone grafting in a furcation defect

Bone Grafting with tacks:

1. Postoperative Care: Provide detailed postoperative instructions to the patient, including oral hygiene measures, dietary restrictions, and medication use (e.g., analgesics, antimicrobials). Schedule follow-up appointments to monitor healing progress and assess the need for any additional interventions.
2. Complications Management: Educate the patient about potential complications such as infection, graft failure, or excessive postoperative pain. Monitor the patient closely for any signs of complications and intervene promptly if necessary.

3. Long-term Maintenance: Emphasize the importance of long-term periodontal maintenance to preserve the results of bone grafting surgery. Regular monitoring and professional cleanings are essential to prevent disease recurrence and maintain periodontal health.
 4. Patient Education: Educate the patient about the rationale behind bone grafting surgery, expected outcomes, and realistic expectations regarding the treatment outcome and timeline for healing.
 5. Collaboration with Specialists: In complex cases, collaborate with other dental specialists such as oral surgeons or prosthodontists to optimize treatment outcomes and provide comprehensive care for the patient.
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